

1 **Two Neoproterozoic tectonothermal events on the western**
2 **edge of the North Atlantic Craton, as revealed by SIMS**
3 **dating of the Saglek Block, Nain Province, Labrador**

4
5 **Abbreviated title: Neoproterozoic tectonothermal events in Labrador**

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19
20 **Abstract:** The Saglek Block comprises the northern part of the Nain Province and underwent
21 widespread metamorphism at *ca.* 2.7 Ga, producing the dominant gneissosity and
22 intercalation of supracrustal sequences. Zircon dating of gneiss samples collected along
23 80 km of the Labrador coast from Ramah Bay in the north to Hebron Fjord in the south
24 confirm the wide spread extent of high-grade metamorphism between 2750 and 2700 Ma. In
25 addition, a distinct event between 2550 and 2510 Ma produced felsic melt with peritectic
26 garnet in metavolcanic gneiss and granoblastic recrystallisation in mafic granulite. Ductile
27 deformation of granite emplaced at *ca.* 2550 Ma indicates that this later event involved a
28 degree of tectonism during high-T metamorphism. Such tectonism may be related to a
29 hypothesised post-2.7 Ga juxtaposition of the predominantly Eoarchean Saglek Block against
30 the Mesoproterozoic Hopedale Block, along a N-S boundary that extends from the coast near
31 Nain to offshore of Saglek Bay. Evidence of reworking of *ca.* 2.7 Ga gneisses by *ca.* 2.5 Ga
32 tectonothermal activity has been found elsewhere on the margins of the North Atlantic Craton

33 (NAC), of which the Nain Province represents the western margin. In particular, a recent
34 suggestion that *ca.* 2.5 Ga metamorphic ages on the northern margin of the NAC in southwest
35 Greenland indicate the time of the final assembly of the craton, may also apply to the western
36 margin.

37

38 Keywords: North Atlantic Craton, Labrador, southwestern Greenland, U-Pb geochronology,
39 zircon, monazite

40

41 **Introduction**

42 The dating of gneissic complexes is commonly complicated by the effects of multiple
43 tectonothermal events, each of which can produce belts of highly-strained, plastically
44 deformed, partially melted and strongly metamorphosed rocks, with previous geological
45 relationships commonly obscured or obliterated. As zones of crustal weakness and/or
46 rheological contrast, such belts are also *loci* for tectonic reactivation, and it is important to
47 decipher the sequence and extent of metamorphic and tectonic events that produced the
48 gneisses if meaningful correlations are to be attempted for disparate terranes that underwent
49 subsequently separate geological histories. Here we present new data on the timing of high-
50 grade metamorphism and deformation in the Archean Nain Province of the North Atlantic
51 Craton (NAC); namely, in the Torngat Mountains region of northern Labrador.

52

53 **Geological setting**

54 The Nain Province (Fig. 1a) consists of Archean gneisses that extend for 500 km along the
55 Labrador coast, from Makkovik to Nachvak Fjord (Taylor 1971), with a likely extension to
56 the Avayalik Islands near the tip of the eastern Labrador Peninsula (Scott 1995). It forms the
57 western margin of the NAC, conjugate to southwestern Greenland prior to the opening of the
58 Labrador Sea (Bridgwater et al. 1973). To the north and west, the Nain Province was
59 reworked at *ca.* 1.8 Ga by the N-S trending Torngat Orogen, which juxtaposed the NAC with
60 Archean continental terranes in the Churchill Province and Paleoproterozoic arc rocks in the
61 Burwell Domain (Van Kranendonk 1996). The Nain Province has been subdivided into the
62 Saglek and Hopedale blocks, north and south, respectively of the town of Nain, (Fig. 1a). In
63 the vicinity of Saglek Bay, tonalite-trondhjemite-granodiorite (TTG) gneisses of the Saglek

64 Block are the product of multiple episodes of high-T metamorphism and ductile deformation
65 that produced a regional dome and basin pattern elongated in a N-S direction, and delineated
66 by interspersed layers and tectonic enclaves composed of supracrustal (metavolcanic and
67 metasedimentary) rocks (Bridgwater et al. 1975; Ryan & Martineau 2012). During the
68 Torngat Orogeny, the Nain Province, along with an unconformably overlying sequence of
69 Paleoproterozoic sediments that include the Ramah Group (Fig. 1), were overthrust by
70 strongly reworked basement gneisses of unknown age (Van Kranendonk & Ermanovics 1990;
71 Rivers et al. 1996).

72 A section of the Saglek Block investigated in recent studies by the same group (Kusiak et al.,
73 2018; Sałacińska et al., 2018, 2019 and Whitehouse et al., 2019) extends for 80 km along the
74 Labrador coast, from Ramah Bay in the north to Hebron Fjord in the south (Fig. 1b). Gneisses
75 in the southern part of the section formed in several stages throughout the Archean, with the
76 oldest and most abundant TTG-type protoliths (the Uivak gneiss) formed between *ca.* 3850
77 and 3600 Ma (Schiøtte et al. 1989; Komiya et al., 2017; Kusiak et al. 2018; Sałacińska et al.
78 2018, 2019), with lesser episodes of felsic plutonism at *ca.* 3.3-3.0 Ga, 2.7 Ga and 2.5 Ga
79 (Schiøtte et al., 1990, 1992; Krogh and Kamo, 2006; Komiya et al., 2015; Sałacińska et al.,
80 2019). Krogh and Kamo (2006) suggested that TTG gneisses from outcrops around Saglek
81 Bay differ in age across the Handy Fault (Fig. 1), with *ca.* 3.6Ga protoliths to the west and *ca.*
82 3.3Ga to the east. However, recent dating (Komiya et al., 2015; Kusiak et al., 2018; Sałacińska
83 et al., 2018, 2019) reveal complicated and tectonised relationships between Eoarchean and
84 younger TTG gneisses on both sides of the fault. Metamorphosed supracrustal assemblages of
85 sedimentary and volcanic rocks, with associated ultramafic gneisses, occur as discontinuous
86 layers within gneissosity typically less than 100 m thick, and have been divided into sparsely
87 distributed pre/syn-Uivak supracrustal rocks (the Nulliak assemblage) and post-Uivak Meso-
88 to Neoarchean Upernavik supracrustal rocks (Bridgwater & Schiøtte 1991). Isotopic U-Pb and
89 Hf data on detrital zircon from Upernavik metasediments indicate deposition after *ca.* 3.0 Ga,
90 and it has been suggested that this unit includes unrelated supracrustal packages with various
91 ages of deposition (Schiøtte et al. 1992). Similarly, there is some uncertainty about the age of
92 deposition of volcanics and sediments that in part formed the Nulliak assemblage. Detrital
93 zircons with an age of *ca.* 3850 Ma (Collerson & Nutman, 1991) supported deposition after
94 that time, but Komiya et al. (2015) and Shimojo et al. (2016) favour a greater antiquity,
95 namely, >3.9 Ga, for these rocks. Whitehouse et al. (2019) have recently questioned this,
96 suggesting that there is confusion over the assignment of metasedimentary and mafic gneisses

97 to the Nulliak or Upernavik 'assemblages'. Graphite-bearing metasediments, claimed by
98 Komiya et al. (2015) to belong to the Nulliak assemblage, contain detrital zircon that
99 demonstrates a much younger provenance (see Whitehouse et al., 2019, after Schiøtte et al.
100 1992). Also, mafic tectonic enclaves near Nulliak Is. that were assigned to the Nulliak
101 assemblage on the map by Ryan and Martineau (2012), have Sm-Nd isotopic signatures that
102 show some of these are much younger than the enclosing Uivak gneiss (Morino et al., 2017).
103 In the absence of more extensive direct dating of tectonic enclaves and belts, the true age of
104 many of the supracrustal rocks in the Saglek Block remains in question.

105 The assembly of the Saglek Block, comprising the Eoarchean Uivak gneiss, Mesoarchean
106 tonalitic to gabbroic gneisses, and supracrustal packages, may be attributed to *ca.* 2.7 Ga
107 tectonism during the widespread high-T metamorphism (Schiøtte et al. 1990; Krogh & Kamo
108 2006; Kusiak et al. 2018; Sałacińska et al. 2018). These studies were mostly focused around
109 Saglek Bay, but *ca.* 2.7 Ga metamorphic zircon was also identified as far south as Drachart
110 Island (Schiøtte et al. 1990), and as far north as the Avayalik Islands near the tip of the eastern
111 Labrador peninsula, where Scott (1995) proposed an extension of the Nain Province as
112 reworked crust within the Torngat Orogen. A corresponding *ca.* 2.7 Ga craton-forming event
113 is recognised in similar gneisses on the conjugate section of southwestern Greenland (e.g.
114 Nutman et al. 2013, 2014; Kirkland et al. 2018).

115 Post-dating the formation of the gneisses in the Saglek Block, 2.5 Ga mineral ages (U-Pb
116 zircon, monazite and titanite, and K-Ar hornblende, see Fig. 8 caption for references) have
117 been attributed to the thermal and hydrothermal effects of post-tectonic granitic magmatism
118 (Baadsgaard et al. 1979; Schiøtte et al. 1992). Alternatively, *ca.* 2.5 Ga monazite and titanite
119 ages from offshore drilling samples collected by Wasteneys et al. (1996), along with
120 *ca.* 2.7 Ga ages of detrital zircon, led Connelly & Ryan (1996) to infer a N-S trending tectonic
121 boundary between the Saglek and Hopedale blocks. The Hopedale Block comprises late
122 Paleoproterozoic to Neoproterozoic protoliths metamorphosed at *ca.* 3.0-2.8 Ga. The inferred
123 boundary with the Saglek Block extends offshore north of Nain; but has not been directly
124 observed, being obscured by the extensive Proterozoic Nain Plutonic Suite. Connelly & Ryan
125 (1996) suggested a link between the Saglek-Hopedale boundary and the Okak shear zone (van
126 Kranendonk & Helmstaedt 1990), 100 kilometres to the north. The Okak shear deforms a
127 granitic pluton on Okak Island (Fig. 1), which was inferred by Schiøtte et al. (1992) to have
128 an age of *ca.* 2.5 Ga (based on unpublished data of Roddick and van Kranendonk) and the age
129 of metamorphic monazite in adjacent metasediments.

130 More recent monazite dating by Kusiak et al. (2018) has increased the known extent of high-
131 temperature metamorphism at both *ca.* 2.7 Ga and *ca.* 2.5 Ga in the Saglek Block between
132 Ramah Bay and Hebron Fjord. However, it is not clear whether these ages represent a
133 prolonged period of high-T metamorphism, a gneiss-forming event with subsequent passive
134 thermal activity and granite emplacement, or two discrete tectonothermal events. The purpose
135 of this paper is to re-evaluate the timing and significance of deformation and metamorphism
136 in the Saglek Block, utilising new U-Pb dating of zircon and monazite.

137

138 **Field relationships**

139 This study investigates the sequence of deformation events in the Saglek Block, based on
140 coastal field work between Ramah Bay and Hebron Fjord (Fig. 1), conducted by our team in
141 2014 and 2017, and the scheme by van Kranendonk & Helmstaedt (1990) for the North River-
142 Nutak area, 100 km south of Saglek Bay. In almost all localities, pre-deformation
143 relationships between the diverse rock types have been transposed into a high-strain
144 gneissosity and a multistage deformational history has long been recognized (Morgan, 1975;
145 Collerson and Bridewater, 1979; Schiøtte et al, 1991). Because gneissosity affects both
146 Eoarchean and younger Archean TTG protoliths, as well as Mesoarchean Upernavik
147 supracrustal rocks, and since published age data indicate widespread zircon and monazite
148 growth during metamorphism at *ca.* 2.7 Ga (Bridgewater & Schiøtte 1991), this may have been
149 the tectonothermal event during which the Saglek Block was assembled. Commonly observed
150 intrafolial folds of gneissic laminations are indications of high-strain ductile deformation (D_1)
151 prior to that which produced the dominant gneissosity (D_2). The dominant gneissosity is in
152 most places vertical to steeply-dipping, with lesser domains of low-angle layering, such as
153 that observed on the cliff face at Cape Uivak (Fig. 2a). The difference between D_1 and D_2
154 structures can be observed where S_2 flattens leucosome in gneisses with S_1 gneissosity and/or
155 mineral foliation (Figs 2b,c,d). Elsewhere, S_1 has been transposed into a high-strain,
156 moderately dipping to sub-vertical gneissic S_2 , that trends predominantly N-S. It is unknown
157 whether D_2 significantly postdates D_1 , but since it transposes D_1 fabrics in late Mesoarchean
158 to early Neoproterozoic Upernavik supracrustal rocks, as well as older TTG gneisses, and no
159 intrusive rocks separate D_1 and D_2 , it likely that they represent stages of a single
160 tectonothermal event. Dating of gneisses with Eoarchean protoliths has established an
161 additional, much older episode of high-grade metamorphism at *ca.* 3.6 Ga (Sałacińska et al.,
162 2018, 2019); however, no large scale structures have been distinguished in the field that relate

163 to this earlier event. In outcrops ~100 km to the south of Saglek Bay, van Kranendonk &
164 Helmstaedt (1990) describe ductile thrusting (F_0) in the Upernavik supracrustal rocks and
165 recumbent folding (F_{n+1}) in both supracrustal rocks and TTG gneisses during high-T, high-P
166 metamorphism. These are low-angle features, in contrast to the predominantly steep N-S
167 trending nature of S_2 gneissosity in most of the Saglek area. Although it is possible that these
168 relate to the low-angle macrofold at Cape Uivak, the latter, along with recumbent folds on
169 nearby Big Is., have been attributed either to nappes produced during late Archean, regional,
170 asymmetric folding that generated the present map pattern (Bridgwater et al., 1975) or else to
171 a separate recumbent folding event superposed on the gneiss pattern produced by the
172 aforementioned asymmetric folding (Bruce Ryan, pers. comm. 2019).

173 Post- D_2 structures tend to be localized. Upright minor folds are found with axial planes
174 parallel to dominant gneissosity, and are interpreted as recording the waning stages of D_2
175 tectonism. There are abundant granitoid stocks, sills and dykes that cut the dominant
176 gneissosity. Such granitoids have been classified by previous authors (Bridgwater & Schiøtte
177 1991; Schiøtte et al. 1992) as ‘post-tectonic’, with deformation attributed to late syn-tectonic
178 magmatism in the waning stages of Neoproterozoic tectonism. However, in many localities
179 between Saglek Bay and Hebron Fjord, granitoid stocks and dykes are strongly deformed,
180 especially on the islands and eastern coastal regions. On Dog Is., coarse metagranite that
181 intrudes Uivak gneiss has a steep S_3 foliation that is axial planar to open F_3 folds where
182 granitic melt has pooled in fold noses (Fig. 2e). Intense L_3 defined by stretching of
183 recrystallized fabrics in both pre- D_2 gneisses and post- D_2 granitoids, indicates high rates of
184 simple shear during the D_3 event. Dynamic recrystallization of granitoid produced augen
185 gneiss 1 km to the east of St. John’s Harbour (Fig. 2f), and the augen show alignment with
186 coarse-grained biotite in quartz and orthoclase. This alignment is parallel to that in the matrix,
187 where quartz, feldspar and biotite have recrystallized into an anastomosing S_3 foliation (Fig.
188 2g). This is consistent with progressive crystallization of the granitoid during a high-strain
189 ductile event. Micro-mylonite shear zones cut across S_3 foliation. There is an increase in D_3
190 strain eastwards and southeastwards from Saglek Bay to the coast, with increasing
191 development of F_3 meso-to-macro folding with variably plunging fold axes and intense L_3
192 stretching and recrystallization parallel to fold axes. Such features are possibly related to D_{n+3}
193 structures described by van Kranendonk & Helmstaedt (1990) further south, which they
194 attribute to a large amphibolite-facies shear zone that runs N-S along the coastal fringe of the
195 Saglek Block south of Saglek Bay to Okak Island, where it deforms syn-tectonic granitic

196 plutons assumed to have intruded around *ca.* 2.5 Ga (Schjøtte et al. 1992). However, this
197 shear zone involves retrogression of granulites to amphibolite-facies gneisses, whereas no
198 such shear zone-related retrogression in association with D₃ structures is observed around
199 Saglek Bay or in granulites around Hebron Fjord.

200

201 **Sample selection and description**

202 Several samples were collected for age determination between Ramah Bay and Hebron Fjord
203 (Fig.1b). Metamorphic grade at these localities varies from amphibolite to granulite facies
204 (Morgan et al., 1979; Ryan and Martineau, 2012), albeit with varying degrees of later lower-
205 grade overprinting, especially around Ramah Bay. The samples include felsic orthogneisses
206 (L1414, L1488, L1489, L1491 and L1493), intermediate orthogneisses having the chemical
207 characteristics of altered volcanic rocks (L1458 and L1487), mafic granulites (L1453 and
208 L1490) and metapelitic gneiss (L1492). A sample of syn-D₃ granitoid (L1412) was also
209 collected. Classification of orthogneisses is based on whole-rock geochemistry, using the
210 Total Alkali vs Silica diagram (Middlemost 1994) for igneous protoliths with <65 wt. % SiO₂,
211 and the ternary normative feldspar classification of Barker (1979; after O'Connor, 1965).
212 Plots are provided with geochemical data in the Appendix. Here, samples are briefly
213 described according to structural relationship and locality (Fig. 1b). Mineral modes and major
214 element geochemistry are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

215 Fine- to medium-grained grey felsic orthogneisses matching the description of Uivak I gneiss
216 were collected from Reichel Head (L1491, L1493), Little Ramah Bay (L1488, L1489) and
217 Dog Island (L1414). All have granoblastic fabrics with S₂ defined by millimetre- to
218 centimetre-scale quartzofeldspathic layers (leucosome) and aligned biotite with or without
219 hornblende. Leucosome consisting of intergrown quartz and feldspar (Fig. 3a) or quartz and
220 mesoperthite (Fig. 2d), which is coarser than the granoblastic fabric in the host gneiss, has
221 resulted from crystallization of partial melt, with minor recrystallisation on grain margins
222 providing evidence of limited subsequent deformation. Samples L1488 and L1489 are
223 representatives of trondhjemitic orthogneisses from Little Ramah Bay that have, respectively,
224 an abundance and a scarcity of nebulitic leucosome. These two samples were combined for
225 the purpose of dating. The leucosome of sample L1414 felsic orthogneiss from Dog Island
226 (Fig. 2b), is stromatic, and the host gneiss varies from a patchily heterogeneous texture
227 interpreted as the recrystallisation of a coarse-grained granitoid (L1414A), to a finer-grained,

228 homogeneous pale grey gneiss with few laminations of leucosome (L1414B). Parts A and B
229 were therefore dated separately.

230 Mafic samples were collected from S_2 layers hosted by TTG orthogneisses at Little Ramah
231 Bay (L1490) and the south shore of Hebron Fjord (L1453). The latter was tentatively assigned
232 by Ryan & Martineau (2012) to the Nulliak supracrustal assemblage, however, the outcrop
233 also contains aluminous metasediments more typical of mafic rocks associated with the
234 Upernavik supracrustal rocks. Both samples have granoblastic texture with two-pyroxene and
235 hornblende-bearing assemblages typical of mafic granulite generated from basaltic protoliths
236 (Fig. 3b), but L1453 has a stronger foliation, with stromatic leucosome and associated garnet-
237 biotite-rich selvages. A sub-vertical NW-trending S_2 gneissosity at the Hebron Fjord locality
238 is crenulated by open to tight F_3 folds with SW-dipping axial planar S_3 defined by aligned
239 biotite and NW-plunging axes. Some patches of garnet-leucosome truncate S_2 but are
240 deformed by D_3 structures, indicating partial melting of mafic orthogneiss during both events.

241 The S_2 gneissosity and stromatic leucosome found in the orthogneisses is also found in
242 sample L1492 of metapelite from Reichel Head (Fig. 2c). The sample is rich in graphite,
243 similar to metasedimentary rocks that have been claimed to be early Eoarchean in age by
244 Tashiro et al. (2017). Garnet poikiloblasts enclose S_2 -aligned flakes of biotite, graphite and
245 sillimanite (Fig. 3c). Leucosome rich in K-feldspar and quartz is also flattened into S_2 , and the
246 mineral assemblage is characteristic of granulite-facies metamorphism.

247 Pyroxene-quartz bearing samples were taken from Little Ramah Bay (L1487) and Upernavik
248 Island (L1458). The former is described by Kusiak et al. (2018), whereas the latter is a typical
249 orthopyroxene-garnet gneiss (Fig. 3d) found interlayered with aluminous and mafic gneisses
250 that forms the Upernavik 'assemblage' (Ryan & Martineau 2012). It is more aluminous than
251 typical andesite, but unlike metapelite from the same locality, it contains abundant
252 orthopyroxene, and is chemically characteristic of altered metavolcanics or volcanoclastics,
253 similar to Mesoarchean deposits at Qussuk and Storø in southwestern Greenland (Szilas et al.
254 2016; Szilas et al. 2017). Composition grades across S_2 gneissic layers from orthopyroxene-
255 plagioclase (L1458A) to garnet-biotite (L1458B) gneiss, however, the difference is in modal
256 proportion only, and all phases are present in both rock types. Abundant leucosome is present
257 in L1458, as S_2 -cutting layers with biotite-rich selvages and euhedral garnet poikiloblasts, as
258 are commonly formed through incongruent melting of pelitic rocks (L1458c; Fig. 3d). Garnet
259 is anhedral and slightly poikilitic in both types, with large inclusions of rutile and quartz (Fig.
260 3e). The leucosome is quartz-rich and moderately deformed, with warped and recrystallized

261 quartz grains wrapping garnet poikiloblasts that contain S₃-aligned grains of biotite and
262 monazite (Fig. 2h). The presence of coarse biotite flakes aligned with the foliation in biotite-
263 rich selvages, and with the sub-mylonitic recrystallization of quartz in the leucosome supports
264 the interpretation that garnet formed through incongruent melting of the host gneiss, and that
265 the melt crystallised under stress.

266

267 **Methods**

268 Detailed analytical protocols and data reduction procedures are provided in the appendix.
269 Bulk rock geochemistry for major elements was undertaken by Acme Labs in Vancouver,
270 Canada, through Bureau Veritas, Poland. For Zr-in-rutile thermometry, electron microprobe
271 analysis was done on a Cameca SX-100 instrument at the Electron Microprobe Laboratory,
272 State Geological Institute of Dionýza Štúra, Bratislava, Slovakia. For ion microprobe
273 analysis, plugs drilled from polished thin sections, and monazite and zircon mineral grains
274 separated from crushed samples, were mounted in epoxy, polished and imaged by Scanning
275 Electron Microscope (SEM) with backscattered electron (BSE) and cathodoluminescence
276 (CL) detectors at the John de Laeter Centre, Curtin University, Western Australia. Isotopic U-
277 Pb dating of zircon and monazite grains was by Sensitive High Resolution Ion MicroProbe
278 (SHRIMP II) at the John de Laeter Centre, Curtin University in Perth, Western Australia, and
279 by CAMECA IMS 1280 ion microprobe at the NordSIMS facility, Swedish Museum of
280 Natural History, Stockholm. All ion microprobe data are quoted with 1 σ analytical errors,
281 whereas weighted mean and discordia intercept ages are quoted at 95% confidence levels, and
282 include the decay-constant error of the concordia curve.

283

284 **Results**

285 **Rutile thermometry**

286 The abundance of rutile in sample L1458 allowed for in situ EMP analysis of zirconium
287 contents in order to estimate temperatures of mineral growth. The formulation of Watson et
288 al. (2006) was used; data are provided in Table 3. Three grains of rutile included in garnet
289 from the garnet-biotite rich part of the sample (L1458B, Fig. 3f) yielded ZrO₂ contents of
290 0.3394 - 0.3622 wt.%, equivalent to 861 - 866°C, whereas grains enclosed in plagioclase or
291 biotite yielded more variable, lower contents (0.1277 - 0.2450 wt.%) equivalent to 747 -
292 817°C. The former temperatures are the best estimate for the temperature of garnet growth

293 during metamorphism on Upernavik Is., and the estimate is consistent with granulite-facies
294 metamorphism in the Saglek Bay area, as has been suggested by various authors (*e.g.* Krogh
295 and Kamo, 2006; Ryan and Martineau, 2012).

296

297 **Zircon dating**

298 Zircon grains from all samples are subhedral to anhedral, with cathodoluminescence (CL)
299 imaging (Fig. 4) revealing rims with anhedral, concentric, graduated or sector zoning typical
300 of growth under high-grade metamorphic conditions. Cores having euhedral, graduated and/or
301 oscillatory growth zoning, typical of crystallisation from an evolving magma, were found in
302 all samples except L1453 (Hebron Fjord) and L1490 (Little Ramah Bay), the latter two
303 having rounded or irregular cores without distinct growth zoning. Sub-grain domains of
304 zircon with features typical of growth during metamorphism were targeted for spot analysis in
305 all samples, and zircon with magmatic growth features were targeted in samples L1412 (near
306 St. Johns Harbour), L1414A/B (Dog Island), L1487 (Little Ramah Bay) and L1491 (Reichel
307 Head). Isotopic U-Pb data (Table 4) are presented in Tera-Wasserburg concordia plots (Fig.
308 5) along with $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ mean ages for concordant populations and Model 1 discordia
309 intercept ages for linear arrays. Older outliers from rounded or irregular cores, which are
310 interpreted as xenocrystic or inherited zircon, were not included in the calculation of ages and
311 statistics from the identified populations. For cores and grains with growth zoning
312 characteristic of igneous zircon, Model 1 discordia chords were calculated with forced lower
313 intercepts of 2720 ± 50 Ma, approximating the time period within which granulite-facies
314 gneisses were estimated to have formed from older magmatic protoliths in the Saglek Block
315 (Kusiak et al., 2018, and references therein). Statistical test values (Mean Square of Weighted
316 Deviates or MSWD) and other details are provided with the concordia plots in Fig. 5.

317 For andesitic orthogneiss L1487 and trondhjemitic orthogneiss L1491, discordia chords yield
318 upper intercept ages of 3664 ± 35 Ma and 3715 ± 26 Ma, respectively. The latter includes five
319 concordant data with a mean $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ age of 3714 ± 11 Ma. Data from zircon in
320 trondhjemitic orthogneiss L1414B spread between *ca.* 3650 and 3590 Ma. Mean $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$
321 ages were also derived from igneous zircon in meta-trondhjemite layer L1414A (2749 ± 3
322 Ma) and meta-monzonite L1412 (2547 ± 3 Ma). In all cases, the estimates are interpreted as
323 the time of crystallization of igneous protoliths, with the exception of L1414B; in that sample,
324 the cluster of analyses at *ca.* 3590 Ma can be interpreted as a maximum age only for the
325 protolith, assuming that they were not disturbed by later metamorphism. Igneous zircon from

326 metapelite L1492 yielded scattered ages between *ca.* 3280 and 2950 Ma, which are
327 interpreted as dating detrital sources for the metasediment, although here again, the possibility
328 of disturbance at *ca.* 2.7 Ga cannot be discounted.

329 Zircon with metamorphic morphologies, either as rims with discordant boundaries to cores or
330 as distinctly equant rounded and sector-zoned grains, yielded statistically valid ($MSWD \leq 1.3$)
331 mean $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ ages for samples of andesitic orthogneiss L1487 (2742 ± 8 Ma),
332 trondhjemitic orthogneiss L1488 (2750 ± 7 Ma), and mafic granulite L1490 (2739 ± 9 Ma).
333 Slightly more scattered data were derived from metapelite L1492 (*ca.* 2750-2720 Ma) and
334 metagranite L1493 (*ca.* 2740-2710 Ma). Two data from light-CL rims in zircon from sample
335 L1414A yielded *ca.* 2710 Ma ages. Together, these data from six samples are interpreted as
336 dating zircon growth during high-T metamorphism between *ca.* 2750 and 2710 Ma. The
337 dataset from mafic granulite sample L1453 is more complex, with 51 analyses from unzoned,
338 concentric and sector-zoned grains and cores ranging between *ca.* 2740 and 2680 Ma (group 1
339 ages, Fig. 5), and 25 data from unzoned or gradationally zoned rims ranging between *ca.* 2570
340 and 2510 Ma (group 2 ages). Analyses in group 1 have variable U contents (Fig. 5), whereas
341 those from group 2 have uniformly low U contents. The groups represent periods of zircon
342 growth during two separate metamorphic events. In order to better define the gap in time
343 between the events, subsets of statistically equivalent data were extracted from the youngest
344 ages in group 1 and the oldest ages in group 2. The 43 youngest out of 51 data in group 1
345 yield a mean $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ age of 2702 ± 2 Ma, and the 20 oldest data out of 25 in group 2 yield
346 a mean $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ age of 2551 ± 6 Ma. These mean ages provide statistically robust estimates
347 for the minimum age of zircon growth in the first metamorphic event, and the maximum age
348 of growth in the second, respectively.

349

350 ***In-situ* monazite dating**

351 In order to constrain the timing of mineral growth in high-grade metamorphic assemblages,
352 plugs containing monazite and surrounding minerals were drilled from polished thin sections,
353 mounted and analysed by SIMS (Table 5, Fig. 5). Monazite in andesitic orthogneiss L1487
354 occurs as xenoblastic grains in a granoblastic assemblage that is strongly retrogressed, as
355 described in Kusiak et al. (2018). Due to the marginal alteration of monazite grains in thin
356 section (Fig. 6a), data were also taken from unaltered fragments of monazite separated from
357 the orthogneiss and mounted in a polished epoxy plug. Excluding three slightly younger,
358 discordant data points, 12 analyses from a combination of grains in drilled thin sections and

359 separates yielded a mean $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ age of 2709 ± 14 Ma. Monazite in metapelite sample
360 L1492 is unaltered and has polygonal grain boundaries with other metamorphic phases (Fig.
361 6b), and yields a mean $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ age of 2727 ± 6 Ma. Ages were also collected from each
362 part of metavolcanic rock L1458 (A, B and C). Two 10 μm -wide monazite inclusions in
363 garnet porphyroblasts from the garnet-biotite rich part (L1458B) yield spot ages of *ca.* 2680
364 and *ca.* 2670 Ma. Monazite occurs more abundantly in association with garnet-leucosome
365 L1458C, in which millimetre-scale preferentially-aligned inclusions in garnet poikiloblasts
366 are parallel to S_3 defined by biotite inclusions (Fig. 6c). Four inclusions of monazite yield
367 ages that range from 2550 to 2510 Ma. Excluding the two oldest analyses, 9 data yield a mean
368 $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ age of 2522 ± 7 Ma, which can be considered as a robust statistical minimum age
369 for the period of metamorphism. Age data were also obtained from monazite separated from
370 the orthopyroxene-rich part (L1458A) and yielded a mean $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ age of 2551 ± 5 Ma.
371 Mean ages from samples L1487 and L1492 are attributed to monazite growth during the first
372 period of high-T metamorphism. Monazite from sample L1458, dated as inclusions in garnet
373 from parts B and C, indicate multiple stages of mineral growth. Those present in cross-cutting
374 garnet-leucosome (L1458C) fall within the second period of mineral growth at 2.5 Ga
375 identified in zircon from other samples in this study, as does monazite in the matrix of part A.
376 The two monazite inclusions in the garnet-biotite rich part (B) fall between the two stages of
377 zircon growth in other samples, but agree with some monazite age estimates obtained by
378 Kusiak et al. (2018). This may be an indication of monazite growth and/or disturbance
379 continuing after 2700 Ma, but as a separate generation from the second stage of growth from
380 2550 to 2510 Ma.

381

382 **Discussion**

383 **Significance and correlation between Labrador and Greenland**

384 The new results from monazite and zircon associated with metamorphic assemblages and
385 deformation fabrics, especially where supported by dating structurally-constrained meta-
386 granitoids, provide evidence of two distinct high-temperature tectonothermal events: at 2750-
387 2700 Ma and 2550-2510 Ma (Fig. 7). The separation of the two episodes of high-T mineral
388 growth is clearer than that observed in EMP monazite dating by Kusiak et al. (2018). There is
389 evidence of partial melting and crystallisation of anatectic melt in both the earlier and later
390 stages of each of the events. Therefore, the growth of zircon and monazite after 2550 Ma is
391 probably not due to the ‘thermal effects’ of granitic emplacement, as suggested by Schiøtte et

392 al. (1992); rather, it is more likely that tectonothermal activity is the progenitor of granitic
393 melts that were emplaced both during and after high-strain deformation. These include the *ca.*
394 2530 Ma major granitic stockworks described by Baadsgaard et al. (1979) on the coast and
395 islands outside Saglek Bay. A re-examination of localities in which *ca.* 2.5 Ga magmatism
396 and mineral growth occurs shows that such ages are scattered along the Saglek Block from
397 Saglek Bay to Nain, and on both sides of the Handy Fault (Fig. 8). Further north there is a
398 lack of data, however, zircon growth during metamorphic events at *ca.* 2.7 Ga and 2.5 Ga
399 have been recognized by Scott (1995) in meta-tonalites near the tip of the Labrador Peninsula,
400 which may be part of the Nain Province. Nevertheless, it is likely that the effects of the 2.5 Ga
401 event increase towards the south and east, as such ages were also obtained from zircon and
402 monazite in drill-core samples taken ~40 km outside Saglek Bay (Wasteneys et al. 1996; see
403 Fig. 8). In that study, the authors hypothesized a N-S trending tectonic boundary between the
404 Saglek and Hopedale blocks that extends southward from offshore of Saglek Bay to the coast
405 near Okak Island. The Saglek Block comprises *ca.* 3.7 Ga protoliths metamorphosed at *ca.*
406 2.7 Ga and the Hopedale Block contains *ca.* 3.2 Ga protoliths metamorphosed at *ca.* 2.5 Ga.
407 Anomalies, such as the presence in the Saglek Block of the *ca.* 3.2 Ga Lister gneiss, from
408 which a migmatized sample yielded *ca.* 2.5 Ga zircon and titanite, have been attributed to
409 tectonic intercalation of fragments of the Hopedale within the Saglek Block at *ca.* 2.5 Ga
410 (Schjøtte et al. 1992; Wasteneys et al. 1996). However, the presence of *ca.* 2680 Ma granitoid
411 sheets cutting folded and metamorphosed Lister gneiss constrains gneiss formation to
412 *ca.* 2.7 Ga (Schjøtte et al., 1989a). This, along with the evidence for *ca.* 2.7 Ga and *ca.* 2.5 Ga
413 metamorphism in samples from the Saglek area in our study and in Kusiak et al. (2018), do
414 not contradict the terrane boundary proposed by Wasteneys et al. (1996), but do suggest that
415 the assembly of the Saglek and Hopedale blocks was earlier than *ca.* 2.5 Ga.

416 The late Archean metamorphic events and the assembly of two different crustal blocks in
417 northern Labrador may be analogous to the juxtaposition of terranes having differing
418 structural and metamorphic histories in the Archean of southwestern Greenland (Nutman and
419 Friend, 2007; Friend and Nutman, 2019). Major late Archean terrane boundaries along the
420 coast of southwestern Greenland tend to run NE into the glacial cap, rather than following the
421 general N-S trend of gneisses in the Saglek area. *Circa* 2.8-2.7 Ga high-grade metamorphism
422 that strongly affects the Nain Province also does so in the vicinity of Nuuk, with grade
423 decreasing towards the east (e.g. Nutman & Friend 2007; Dziggel et al. 2017). This part of the
424 NAC contains a complex mixture of Eoarchean and Paleoarchean terranes, and Mesoarchean

425 arc assemblages, and has many similarities in timing and composition with the gneisses of the
426 Saglek Block. The extensive *ca.* 2560 Ma Qôrqt Granite Complex that intrudes gneisses
427 inland from Nuuk (Nutman et al. 2011; Næraa et al. 2014), is a potential correlative of syn- to
428 late-D₃ magmatism in the Saglek block, since marginal tectonic re-working of the Qôrqt has
429 been observed (Nutman et al. 2011). However, no significant metamorphic event at *ca.* 2.5 Ga
430 is recognized in this part of Greenland. Approximately 100 km to the north, dating of
431 *ca.* 2.5 Ga metamorphic monazite in gneisses near Maniitsoq and inland led Dyck et al.
432 (2015) to define the Majorqaq Belt, a NE-trending mobile belt between the main 2.7 Ga-
433 assembled part of the NAC and the Mesoarchean Maniitsoq block further north. Dyck et al.
434 (2015) suggest that the belt resulted from the collision of the Maniitsoq block subsequent to
435 southward subduction of an ocean basin beneath the NAC, and that the Qôrqt Granite
436 Complex is the product of slab dewatering. The Majorqaq Belt might well correlate with
437 *ca.* 2.5 Ga tectonothermal activity in the Saglek Block. In this case, the Qôrqt Granite
438 Complex would correlate well with large plutons of the same age found to the south of Saglek
439 in the Okak area (Schjøtte et al. 1992). Indeed, the Maniitsoq block itself was subjected to
440 marginal reworking to the north by Paleoproterozoic tectonism, similar to the northern and
441 western margins of the Nain Province (St-Onge et al. 2009). However, there is a lack of data
442 from the Labrador coast north of Ramah Bay that would allow any clear correlation to be
443 made with the hypothesised ‘Majorqaq’ Belt. In addition, this would dissociate the Eoarchean
444 Uivak gneiss from terranes of similar age in the Itsaq Gneiss Complex (Fig. 8). The latter has
445 complicated ductile structural relationships with Paleo- to Mesoarchean terranes (Hoffmann et
446 al. 2014). If such relationships are similarly complicated in the Saglek Block, the intercalation
447 of older and younger crust there may also be a product of amalgamation at *ca.* 2.7 Ga. A
448 simpler correlation would place *ca.* 2.5 Ga tectonothermal activity as a reworking of
449 *ca.* 2.7 Ga gneisses in association with the Okak and Qôrqt granitic complexes, on the
450 eastern and southern margins of a composite Eoarchean-Mesoarchean continent. To test this
451 hypothesis, geochronological work needs to be extended further north along the Labrador
452 coast, and to little-studied parts of southwestern Greenland.

453

454 **Conclusion**

455 *In-situ* U-Pb ion microprobe dating of monazite, and sub-grain dating of zircon and monazite,
456 provide clear evidence of high-T metamorphism at both *ca.* 2.7 Ga and *ca.* 2.5 Ga in the
457 Saglek Block. Both events involve ductile deformation, with the former producing the

458 dominant gneissosity in the Uivak and other gneisses, including supracrustal metasedimentary
459 and metavolcanic varieties. The effects of tectonothermal activity at *ca.* 2.7 Ga are widespread
460 in the Saglek Block, as they are in the parts of southwestern Greenland conjugate to the Nain
461 Province before the opening of the Labrador Sea. The known extent of *ca.* 2.5 Ga high-T
462 metamorphism and deformation is more limited, and may be restricted to reworking of the
463 margins of the North Atlantic Craton in both Greenland and Labrador. However, given the
464 emplacement of large amounts of *ca.* 2.5 Ga granitoid in both Labrador and southwestern
465 Greenland, it is possible that parts of the North Atlantic Craton were assembled at this time,
466 involving the juxtaposition of pre-existing continental crust in Labrador (the Saglek and
467 Hopedale blocks of the Nain Province) and Greenland (between the Maniitsoq Block and
468 others to the south). The evidence for late Neoproterozoic final assembly is still very limited, and
469 will require extensive new geochronological studies in both Labrador and Greenland.

470 This study also provides zircon ages for the formation of supracrustal precursors to gneisses
471 in the Saglek Block 30 km to the north of Saglek Bay. A protolith age of *ca.* 3.7 Ga for
472 andesitic orthogneiss at Little Ramah Bay is comparable to Eoarchean ages for the Uivak
473 gneiss have been well established by many earlier studies. *Circa* 3 Ga ages from detrital
474 zircon in graphite-bearing metapelitic gneiss from Reichel Head are comparable to those
475 obtained from similar gneiss at St. John's Harbour, and support the conclusion of Whitehouse
476 et al. (2019) that such graphite-bearing gneisses were not deposited at the beginning of the
477 Archean, as proposed by Tashiro et al. (2019). These ages provide new evidence for the
478 northward continuation of the Saglek Block, and demonstrate the potential for new
479 discoveries of Eoarchean crust along the Labrador Coast.

480

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745 **Figure captions**

746 **Fig. 1. (a)** The western part of the North Atlantic Craton (NAC), dotted line (after St-Onge et
747 al., 2009). The location of study area within the Nain Province on the margin of the NAC is
748 shown. **(b)** Sketch map of part the Saglek Block investigated in this study.

749

750 **Fig. 2.** Macro-to microscopic structural relationships in the Saglek Block. **(a)** View of Cape
751 Uivak to southwest, showing macroscopic recumbent fold (possibly F_2) defined by a tens of
752 metres-thick layer of mafic orthogneiss (M) and disrupted by webby networks of post- D_2
753 granite (G). Fold nose closes to left as shown in the inset sketch; to the right, the limbs are
754 parallel to dominant S_2 gneissosity in Uivak gneiss (U). Gneisses are intruded by sub-vertical
755 Proterozoic 'Dome' (D) and Phanerozoic (P) mafic dykes. Width of view (WOV)
756 approximately 800m; cliff on right is around 350m high. **(b)** Intense vertical composite $S_{2/1}$
757 gneissosity in grey Uivak gneiss on Dog Is., with transposed S_2 granitic laminations. WOV
758 1m. Inset: close-up of lower right after sampling, matching division of sample L1414 into part
759 A (coarser metagranitic gneiss with S_2 -flattened and recrystallized patches of mafic phases) and
760 part B (grey gneiss with stronger $S_{2/1}$ gneissosity. **(c)** Intense vertical S_2 gneissosity and
761 foliation defined by biotite and sillimanite in metapelitic gneiss, Reichel Head. WOV 30 cm.
762 Inset: Sample L1492 of metapelite. **(d)** Crossed polars microphotograph of mesoperthite in
763 S_2 -flattened granitic lamination from sample L1491 of grey Uivak gneiss, Reichel Head.
764 WOV 3 mm. Inset: sample L1491, with granitic lamination in trondhjemitic grey gneiss. **(e)**
765 Intrusion of coarse-grained metagranite (G) across $S_{2/1}$ gneissosity in grey Uivak gneiss, prior
766 to or during D_3 folding and formation of axial planar S_3 . Dog Is, WOV 1m. **(f)** Steep N-
767 trending S_3 foliation and recrystallization in metagranite 1km southeast of St John's Harbour.
768 WOV 40 cm. Inset: sample L1412 of metagranite. **(g)** Crossed polars microphotograph of
769 sample L1412, showing margin of magmatic orthoclase including biotite aligned parallel to S_3
770 foliation defined by biotite in matrix. A mylonite microplane (S_{myl}) cuts S_3 across the lower
771 half of the image. WOV 3 mm. **(h)** Polished thin section from sample L1458C of
772 metavolcanic gneiss, Upernavik Is. Garnet porphyroblast contains inclusions of biotite,
773 monazite and other minerals aligned with strong S_3 foliation in adjacent coarse-grained
774 biotite. Circle shows area drilled for *in situ* monazite dating. Mineral abbreviations: Qz =
775 quartz, Kfs = K-feldspar, Per = Perthite, Or = orthoclase, Bt = biotite, Grt = garnet, Mnz =
776 monazite.

777

778 **Fig. 3.** Mineral relationships in gneisses of the Saglek block. All are photomicrographs except
779 (d). **(a)** Coarsely recrystallized weak S_2 fabric in metagranitic lamination from sample
780 L1414A, Dog Is. Prismatic zircon crystal is aligned parallel with S_2 . Plagioclase has been
781 strongly sericitised. Crossed polars, WOV 3mm. **(b)** Granoblastic texture in sample L1490,
782 mafic granulite from Little Ramah Bay, with extensive alteration of mafic minerals and
783 sericitisation of plagioclase. Crossed polars, WOV 4mm. **(c)** Porphyroblastic texture in
784 sample L1492 of metapelite from Reichel Head. Dark clot is an intergrowth of graphite,
785 spinel, magnetite, ilmenite and cordierite. Transmitted light, WOV 2cm. **(d)** Outcrop
786 photograph of metavolcanic gneiss, showing rock types (A, B and C) found in sample L1458
787 from Upernavik Is. Type A is granoblastic orthopyroxene and garnet-bearing gneiss (bottom);
788 type B is garnet and biotite-rich gneiss (top); type C is felsic neosome with idioblastic garnet
789 (middle). Note biotite selvages around garnet idioblasts and on the margins of the neosome,
790 formed by back-reaction during crystallization of felsic melt. WOV 15cm. **(e)** Xenoblastic
791 garnet in sample L1458A, in granoblastic gneiss with rutile, plagioclase and orthopyroxene;
792 the latter occurs as both xenoblasts and discontinuous rims between garnet and plagioclase.
793 Transmitted light, WOV 4mm. **(f)** Backscattered electron (BSE) image of sample L1458B,
794 showing rutile inclusions in garnet and biotite. Zirconium-in-rutile temperature estimates
795 obtained by electron microprobe. Mineral abbreviations: Qz = quartz, Zrn = zircon, Pl =
796 Plagioclase, Opx = orthopyroxene, Cpx = clinopyroxene, Hbl = hornblende, Mag =
797 magnetite, Kfs = K-feldspar, Grt = garnet, Bt = biotite, Sil = sillimanite, Grp = graphite, Spl =
798 spinel, Ilm = ilmenite, Crd = cordierite, Rt = rutile.

799

800 **Fig. 4.** Cathodoluminescence images of zircon dated by secondary ion mass spectrometry
801 (SIMS). Labels show sample and grain numbers; analytical spots labelled with type of zircon
802 (m = metamorphic, i = igneous, x = xenocrystic, d = detrital) and $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ age.

803

804 **Fig. 5.** Tera-Wasserburg concordia plots of SIMS age data from zircon and monazite. Spot
805 ages represented by error ellipses are colour-coded according to type: green = *ca.* 2.7 Ga
806 metamorphic; blue = *ca.* 2.5 Ga metamorphic; red/pink = igneous; grey =
807 xenocrystic/inherited; tan = detrital. See text for details.

808

809 **Fig. 6.** Microimaging of monazite dated *in situ* by SIMS. **(a)** Grain 8 in sample L1487 of
810 andesitic orthogneiss, Little Ramah Bay, with thin dual corona of apatite and allanite/epidote
811 against enclosing assemblage of biotite (altered to chlorite), plagioclase, quartz and pyrite.
812 Backscattered electron (BSE) photo, WOV 0.3mm. **(b)** Grains 1 and 2 in sample L1492 of
813 metapelite, Reichel Head, with polygonal and interstitial relationships to plagioclase, apatite,
814 and zircon. Chlorite replaces biotite. BSE image, WOV 0.2mm. **(c)** S₄-aligned grains 11 and
815 12 in garnet idioblast, sample L1458C of neosome vein in metavolcanic gneiss, Upernavik Is.
816 Biotite and monazite grains included in garnet are aligned with S₄; marginal recrystallization
817 in quartzose neosome and orthogonal fracturing in idioblastic garnet indicates deformation
818 after crystallization of melt, possibly during late D₃. Crossed polars, WOV 12mm. Inset: *in*
819 *situ* BSE image of disc drilled for SIMS analysis – *cf.* Fig. 2 (h). Mineral abbreviations: Qz =
820 quartz, Py = pyrite, Bt = biotite, Aln = allanite, Ap = apatite, Zrn = zircon, Pl = Plagioclase,
821 Chl = chlorite, Grt = garnet.

822

823 **Fig. 7.** Histogram of combined ²⁰⁷Pb/²⁰⁶Pb spot ages from SIMS analysis of metamorphic
824 zircon and monazite in multiple samples. **(a)** L1412, L14014A-B, L1453, L1487, L1488/89,
825 L1492; **(b)** L1458, L1487, L1492

826

827 **Fig. 8.** Reconstruction of the western part of the North Atlantic Craton, modified after St-
828 Onge et al. (2009), and showing the location of magmatic and metamorphic mineral ages (U-
829 Pb zircon, monazite and titanite ages, and K-Ar hornblende ages) that fall within the
830 *ca.* 2.7 Ga and 2.5 Ga events, and the approximate known extent of *ca.* 2.7 Ga metamorphism
831 in the Nain Province and southwestern Greenland. A hypothetical boundary between the
832 Hopedale and Saglek blocks, slightly modified from that proposed by Connelly and Ryan
833 (1996) and Wasteneys et al (1996) is shown by dotted line, parallel to the Handy Fault.
834 Terranes in southwestern Greenland (bound by black lines) and the extent of Proterozoic
835 orogenic fronts (thick black lines) are from Henriksen et al. (2009). Age data from: Wanless
836 et al. (1970, 1974); Barton (1975); Collerson et al. (1982); Schiøtte et al. (1990); Schiøtte et
837 al. (1992); Scott (1995); Connelly & Ryan (1996); Wasteneys et al (1996); Wendt &
838 Collerson (1999); Connelly (2001); Rosing et al. (2001); Krogh & Kamo (2006); Nutman et
839 al. (2004); Nutman & Friend (2007); Nutman et al. (2011); Nutman et al. (2013); Næraa et al.
840 (2014); Dyck et al. (2015); Dziggel et al. (2017); Kirkland et al. (2018); Kusiak et al. (2018);
841 Sałacińska et al. (2018).

842

843 **Appendix**

844 **Analytical protocols**

845 Polished thin sections from all samples were prepared and examined by optical microscope
846 and Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) at the John de Laeter Centre, Curtin University,
847 Western Australia. For *in situ* monazite analysis (samples L1458 and L1487), 3 and 5mm
848 discs were drilled out of thin sections and mounted in epoxy discs. For mineral grain dating,
849 samples were crushed and sieved, and then processed by wet panning, magnetic separation
850 and hand picking to isolate zircon and monazite grains. The grains were mounted, along with
851 reference materials in epoxy discs that were then polished to expose the mid-sections of
852 grains. All grains were imaged for internal structure before and after analysis using an SEM
853 fitted with backscattered electron (BSE) and cathodoluminescence (CL) detectors. The
854 mounts were cleaned and gold coated prior to analysis by SIMS (Secondary Ion Mass
855 Spectrometry).

856 Initial dating of mounted zircon grains was done by Sensitive High Resolution Ion
857 MicroProbe (SHRIMP II) at the John de Laeter Centre, Curtin University in Perth, Western
858 Australia. A spot size of 20 to 25 μm was used with an O_2^- primary beam intensity of 3 to 4
859 nA. The secondary ion beam was focused through a 100 μm collector slit onto an electron
860 multiplier to produce mass peaks with flat tops and a mass resolution (1% peak height) better
861 than 5100 $M/\Delta M$. Data were collected in sets of six scans, with reference standards analyzed
862 after every five sample analyses. Count times per scan for Pb isotopes 204, background
863 position 204.1, 206, 207, and 208, were 10, 10, 10, 30, and 10 s, respectively. U-Th-Pb ratios
864 and absolute abundances were determined relative to the zircon reference standard BR266
865 (559 Ma, 903 ppm U; Stern (2001)). Instrumental mass fractionation (IMF) of $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ was
866 monitored during each session by repeated analysis of the zircon reference standard OGC
867 (Stern et al. 2009). No IMF correction was required because the measured values of OGC
868 were in agreement with the reference value within 2σ uncertainty. Raw data were processed
869 using the SQUID 2 add-in (v. 2.50.12.03.08) for Excel 2003 (Ludwig 2009) and plotted using
870 the ISOPLOT 3.70 add-in of Ludwig (2001). Measured compositions were corrected for
871 common Pb using measured ^{204}Pb and contemporaneous common Pb composition according
872 to the terrestrial Pb evolution model of Stacey & Kramers (1975). Due to the low proportion
873 of common Pb detected in standards and samples (<1% of measured ^{206}Pb , as estimated from
874 ^{204}Pb measurement), the choice of modelling age for common Pb composition did not have a

875 statistically significant effect on age estimates. Mean ages are quoted with 95% confidence
876 levels.

877 Further analysis of zircon in samples L1412, L1414, L1453, L1488-89, L1490, L1491, L1492
878 and L1493 was done by CAMECA IMS 1280 ion microprobe at the NordSIMS facility,
879 Swedish Museum of Natural History, Stockholm. Protocols for U-Pb data closely follow
880 published methodology (Whitehouse & Kamber 2005). Zircon grains were analysed using a
881 *ca.* 15 μm , 6 nA O_2^- primary beam, and peak-hopping monocollection in an ion counting
882 electron multiplier (EM) at a mass resolution of approximately 5400 $M/\Delta M$. Reference
883 material 91500 (1065 Ma, 80 ppm of U; Wiedenbeck et al. 1995) was used for calibration of
884 Pb/U ratios using the Pb/UO vs. UO_2/UO calibration protocol of Jeon & Whitehouse (2015).
885 Common Pb was corrected using the ^{204}Pb counts assuming a present-day terrestrial Pb-
886 isotope composition model (Stacey & Kramers 1975) following the rationale of Zeck &
887 Whitehouse (1999) that this is largely surface contamination introduced during sample
888 preparation and not common Pb residing in zircon and/or micro-inclusions. Very low
889 amounts of common Pb were detected during the spot analyses with $f^{206}\text{Pb} < 0.1\%$, in many
890 cases below detection limit for ^{204}Pb based on the electron multiplier background. Where
891 common Pb corrections were deemed necessary on the basis of measurable ^{204}Pb ($> 3x$
892 standard deviation on the average background), these were small and therefore insensitive to
893 the precise composition of common Pb. Data reduction was performed using the NordSIMS-
894 developed suite of software of M.J. Whitehouse. All ion microprobe data are quoted with 1σ
895 analytical errors, whereas weighted mean and discordia intercept ages are quoted at 95%
896 confidence levels, and include the decay-constant error of the concordia curve.

897 For *in situ* (*i.e.* within polished thin section) and grain mount monazite analysis, the SHRIMP
898 II was operated with a primary beam of O_2^- ions focused through a 50 μm Kohler aperture to
899 produce an oval 10 μms wide spot with a surface current of 0.2 to 0.4nA. Secondary
900 ionisation was measured without energy filtering on a single electron multiplier on 13 mass
901 stations from 202 (LaPO_2) to 270 (UO_2), with a mass resolution of >5200 for the latter.
902 Secondary ion retardation was used to eliminate ion scatter. Mass stations 202 (LaPO_2), 203
903 (CePO_2), 205.9 (NdPO_2), 232 (Th), 244.8 (YCeO) and 264 (ThO_2) were analysed for matrix
904 corrections and interference on ^{204}Pb , following the protocols outlined in Fletcher et al.
905 (2010). Mass stations were measured through 6 cycles, with typical count times of 10s per
906 cycle for ^{204}Pb , background (at 204.04 amu) and ^{206}Pb , 30s for ^{207}Pb and 5s for ^{208}Pb .
907 Reduction of raw data for standards and samples was performed using the SQUID 2.5 and

908 Isoplot 3.70 add-ins for Microsoft Excel 2003 (Ludwig 2001, 2009). Age ($^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$) and
909 abundance of U were calibrated against reference monazite French (514 Ma; 1000ppm U).
910 High La and high Y-Nd-U standards Z2234 and Z2908, respectively, were used for matrix
911 and interference corrections, following the method described in Fletcher et al. (2010).
912 Corrections for common Pb on isotopic U/Pb values and ages were carried out with common
913 Pb estimated from ^{204}Pb counts and the composition of Broken Hill lead.

914 For Zr-in-rutile thermometry, electron microprobe analysis was undertaken at the Electron
915 Microprobe Laboratory, State Geological Institute of Dionýza Štúra, Bratislava, Slovakia,
916 utilizing a Cameca SX-100 electron microprobe equipped with four wavelength-dispersive
917 spectrometers. Large high-sensitivity, LPET and LLIF crystals and a conventional TAP
918 crystal were used for analysis. Analytical conditions were chosen to balance the best
919 analytical conditions against reasonable acquisition times. An accelerating voltage of 15 kV
920 was used, with a probe current of 200 nA. Zirconium contents were calibrated against an in-
921 house standard.

922
923 Geochemistry: see attached Excel file.